

Education Quarterly Reviews

Aboudahr, S. M. F. M. & Benlahcene, A. (2023). Learner's Perception in Using Social Media for Foreign Languages Acquisition. *Education Quarterly Reviews*, 6(1), 191-197.

ISSN 2621-5799

DOI: 10.31014/aior.1993.06.01.698

The online version of this article can be found at:
<https://www.asianinstituteofresearch.org/>

Published by:
The Asian Institute of Research

The *Education Quarterly Reviews* is an Open Access publication. It may be read, copied, and distributed free of charge according to the conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

The Asian Institute of Research *Education Quarterly Reviews* is a peer-reviewed International Journal. The journal covers scholarly articles in the fields of education, linguistics, literature, educational theory, research, and methodologies, curriculum, elementary and secondary education, higher education, foreign language education, teaching and learning, teacher education, education of special groups, and other fields of study related to education. As the journal is Open Access, it ensures high visibility and the increase of citations for all research articles published. The *Education Quarterly Reviews* aims to facilitate scholarly work on recent theoretical and practical aspects of education.

ASIAN INSTITUTE OF RESEARCH
Connecting Scholars Worldwide

Learner's Perception in Using Social Media for Foreign Languages Acquisition

Shorouk Mohamed Farag Mohamed Aboudahr¹, Abderrahim Benlahcene²

¹ Faculty of Education & Humanities, Unitar International University. Email: shorouk@unitar.my

² Department of psychology, College of humanities and sciences, Ajman University, UAE. Email: a.benlahcene@ajman.ac.ae

Abstract

Social media use is a crucial component of modern education. The overuse of social media has completely captivated learners' attention. This study conducted to examine the perception of foreigner language learners toward utilization of social media. This descriptive study's data was gathered using a qualitative approach with a custom-made questionnaire. 60 students participated in this study. The study's findings demonstrated that learners' regular use of social media had a substantial impact on their performance. It has also showed that, and learners had positive attitude toward using social media in order to acquisition of foreigner language. Therefore, one of the educational tools that learners can use to improve their foreign language skills is social media. This study offers insights into how important of technology to support learner the integration and utilization of social media platforms as instructional tools in the context of acquisition foreign languages.

Keywords: Learner's Perception, Social Media, Foreign Languages

1. Introduction

The quick advancement of technology has aided the development of rapidly expanding social media tools, which are increasingly being used by students in social and academic settings. In Teaching and Learning, social networking sites are seen as beneficial in language acquisition because their community-centred design encourages meaningful interactions outside of the classroom and fosters the transmission of real language. Teaching and learning are currently being made more engaging and exciting through the use of technology (Manca, 2020). According to global digital statistics in 2017, with 10% annual growth, more than half of the world now uses smartphones and more than half of the world's web traffic comes from mobile phones with broadband mobile connections (Ceci, 2022). Similar to this, the 2016 International Telecommunication Union research shows that 84% of the world's population can access mobile broadband networks (3G or higher) and that 95% of people worldwide live in areas served by mobile cellular networks (ITU, 2020). Since the millennium generation tends to employ mobile technologies in all part of their lives, it goes without saying that modern educational procedures are being built and modified in response to these advancements.

There are various websites and platforms are affecting communication, information delivery, knowledge exchange, commerce, education, and all different aspects of life such as Facebook, YouTube, Twitter, WhatsApp, and telegram which becoming a part of the teaching and learning process (Rieger and Christoph, 2018; Bhatti et al., 2019; Amin et al., 2020) Several research studies have been carried out in the field of education to determine their efficacy in various fields. As young users of social media networks spend more than half of their days using and interacting on these networking sites using their language and communication skills, the influx of linguistic output on social media represents numerous opportunities for language learners to process language and obtain input (Al Jahromi, 2020).

As a result, face-to-face conversations have been supplanted by online chats and discussions, both written and spoken, which has had a significant impact on users' everyday language and linguistic abilities. The widespread use of smartphones, laptops, and tablets coupled with popular social media platforms may have made rich linguistic input available at the users' fingertips and helped to produce understandable second language output (Al Jahromi, 2020; Pikhart and Botezat, 2021). There aren't many studies that examine social media's effects on learning and education, particularly in the context of foreign language, despite the fact that it will undoubtedly have an impact on people's lives everywhere and that today's students are disinterested in traditional teaching methods and learning strategies. Determining the effect of social media on learning second language is the goal of the current study. Therefore, based on the background stated above, the researcher will further discuss how social media platforms can affect the learning of a foreign language positively.

2. Social Media and Learning foreign languages

The advancement of social media has widened the students' access to education through formal and informal learning environments (Herri & Gunawan, 2020). According to many authors, integrating advanced social media into educational settings will not only enable unrestricted communication and interaction between students and teachers as well as between students themselves (Blaine, 2019; Kazanidis et al., 2018), but will also help students become more interested in and motivated to demonstrate mastery of learning outcomes (Rozal et al., 2021). In the field of education, employing social media tools to enhance both formal and informal learning has particularly been advised in the literature.

According to Lambton-Howard et al., (2021), social media is generally conceded to be the most popular way to communicate and learn foreign languages. Students easily accept the integration of social media in educational practice. For example, Blaine (2019) and Simamora (2020) emphasised that the social media gives every student the opportunity to show independence in learning; The instructor controls the learning process in an interactive mode; Studies by Shodiyev (2022) identified the importance of social media as part of the linguistic educational environment in teaching a foreign language. There is constant and immediate feedback for both the teacher and the students; In a foreign language lesson, group interaction is planned, and the teacher facilitates the students' learning activities; You can develop your academic independence through a variety of online activities. Also, Social media, according to Chugh and Ruhi (2018), facilitates peer-to-peer learning, encourages the sharing of educational resources, and fosters an increase in student contact and participation. Yunus et al., (2019) also reported that the advantage of social media helps develop students' writing ability. Jenaibi and Mansoori (2022) contended that social media context allows learners to manage and maintain a learning space that facilitates their learning activities and connections to peers and social networks across time and place. To achieve this aim, the present work specifically seeks to investigate the following research objectives.

To investigate to what extent social media platforms can affect the learning of a foreign language positively.

To examine how foreign language learners use social media for learning second language.

To what extent social media influence learners' performance.

3. Theoretical Background

Social learning theory have been used to adopt social media in teaching and learning foreign languages. On the basis of social learning theory, a major tenet of the social learning theory advocates that people are impelled to

undertake and accomplish a task they feel confident in performing. The instinctive perception of behaviors that induce positive results depicts an individual's self-efficacy (Bandura, 1982; Schunk, 2011).

According to the behavioral theory about learning, learning always occurred within a social context. Learning Theories Knowledgebase Edgar (2012) states that According to Bandura's Social Learning Theory, people pick up knowledge from one another through modelling, imitation, and observation. The theory, which takes into account attention, memory, and motivation, has frequently been referred to as a bridge between behaviourist and cognitive learning theories.

Therefore, learners understand by imitating the actions, attitudes, and results of others. As stated by Bandura (1982), "learning would be exceedingly laborious, not to mention hazardous, if people had to rely solely on the effects of their own actions to inform them what to do. Fortunately, most human behavior is learned observationally through modeling; from observing others, one forms an idea of how new behaviors are performed, and on later occasions, this coded information serves as a guide for action". (p. 22). A review of the literature on the integration of theory and practice within the social learning discovered several studies that found that student who's learning through social media felt that their learning process more adequately prepared them for real world practice.

An online environment has provided learners with more social contact with each other, hence the greater opportunities to learn from others and to be influenced to a greater extent (Chatterjee & Correia, 2020). This environment has offered the opportunity for teachers and students from all over the place to unite and develop communities of practice in their areas of research (Scavarelli et al., 2021). Moreover, online education could provide educators more opportunities enlarge and enhance his or her knowledge (Sepulveda-Escobar & Morrison, 2020). Kuo et al., (2022) revealed that after undergoing the web-based education using self-regulatory strategies, learners become more self-assured, challengeable, and highly assessing of what they learnt.

4. Methodology

The main objective of the current study is to determine how different social media platforms affect learning a foreign language, as well as to highlight any potential improvements to future virtual language learning. In the light of that, the study applied quantitative approach by using descriptive analysis method to analyse the research objectives by calculating the percentages from the answers to each question. The questionnaire was used, with multiple choice items coming last and open-ended and closed-ended questions coming first. 60 people made up the study's population; 40.4% of the men and 59.6% of the women who volunteered to learn a foreign language on Facebook were men.

5. Results and Discussion

A questionnaire sent to students who are currently learning a foreign language through social media served as the main source of data gathering. Based on the results of the study obtained data that there is a significant impact of using social media on learning foreign language. The findings show that most participants use social media as a tool for language acquisition.

The pie chart below shows that there are five languages that learner willing to acquisition. Overall, English language being the highest percentage with (30%) follow by Arabic language with (25%) of the population while Chinese was the lowest percentage of learner with (13%).

In terms of second question the results shows that the learners who believe social media can have a positive impact on learning a foreign language. The findings imply that social media is a common method of language acquisition among participants. Approximately, 96.6% of the learners think that social media can have a positive influence on learning foreign language, while 3.4% think it can have a detrimental impact on the language learning process shows figure 1.

Figure 1: Do you think that social media platforms (e.g., Facebook, WhatsApp, Twitter, Instagram, Google and etc.: can affect learning foreign languages positively.

The result of question 3 reveals that majority of participant use several platforms in order to learn for instant as figure 2 displayed one participant use 1platform for learning while 12 of learner used two, 8 participants used 5 platforms, 16 utilized 4 and majority of participant used.

Figure 2: How many Social Media platforms do you use.

The answer to the fourth question revealed that, according to the data, WhatsApp has the highest percentage of users of any social networking site, as seen in Figure 3 above. Second in terms of popularity is Facebook. Additionally, some students use platforms like Twitter, Instagram, LinkedIn, and Wechat, among other social media sites that they prefer to use.

Figure 3: Which of the following social media platforms do you use

The next question results exposed that pertaining to the usage of social media as a communication tool during the learning process is shown in Figure 4 below. According to the findings, 91.5% of learners prefer to use social media platforms for learning. They think that social media gives pupils the opportunity to communicate with one another and with their friends. However, 8.5% of respondents said they didn't use social media for learning since they didn't think it helped with their studies. They think that the purpose of these platforms is to increase their sense of community.

Figure 4: Would you be interested in using social media platforms as an educational tool.

The results in figure 5 show that most learners are enthusiastic about adopting social media as a teaching tool, and that a higher percentage of students approximately 54.2 and 33.9%—use social media to study foreign languages at "good" and "excellent" rates, respectively. It is further claimed that none of the learners assessed the use of social media platforms on learning a foreign language as being poor, and only 11.9% of the leaerers percentage the use of social media on learning foreign languages as "average".

Figure 5: How would you rate the use of social media platforms on learning a foreign language. The final question explores how social networking sites affect learners' academic performance. 52.2% of the participants said that social networking sites had a significant impact on their studies, according to the data, while 42.2% said that social networking sites had just a minor impact on their performance and language proficiency. However, 18.07% of the students concurred that social networking sites have no influence on their academic performance. Figure 6 below illustrates how social networking sites are influencing students' academic performance.

Figure 6: influence of social media on learners' performance

6. Conclusion

The current study aims to examine the most significant effects of using social media for foreign language acquisition. Based on the result has shown that there has been a change to teaching and learning methodology in which traditional face-to-face teaching and learning have been replaced with new methods of online teaching that use information technology. The study concluded that since the outbreak of online learning, there are a number of platforms have appeared to ease the teaching and learning of foreign language processes. Consequently, the Process of teaching and learning foreign languages can be conducted at any time anywhere.

Furthermore, the study revealed that social media can be used as a beneficial communication and teaching tool since the learner is not constrained by specific learning situations. This finding is consistent with how foreign language learners perceive social media. Additionally, numerous foreign language learner use this method to advance their practises because of the significant options it offers.

The study recommended that social media should be used by students and instructors as a tool for experiential, contextual learning and as social practises deserving of critical attention because it is becoming more commonplace and omnipresent. Therefore, it is necessary to continue investigating how certain media and situational factors might amplify, activate, diminish, or nullify technologically agnostic social media dynamics.

References

- Al Jahromi, D. (2020). A quantitative study of the perceived impact of social media networks on Bahraini users' English language learning. *Teaching English with Technology*, 20(4), 23-40.
- Amin, B., Rafiq, R. and Mehmood, N. (2020). The impact of social media in English language learning. *Journal of Critical Reviews*, 7(10), 3126-3135, doi: 10.31838/jcr.07.10.507.
- Bhatti, A., Bano, T. and Rehman, S.-U. (2019). Social media and consumer satisfaction effect on consumer purchase intention with the moderating role of trust. *International Journal of Business Management*, 4 (2), 131-141.
- Blaine, A. M. (2019). Interaction and presence in the virtual classroom: An analysis of the perceptions of students and teachers in online and blended Advanced Placement courses. *Computers & Education*, 132, 31-43.
- Bandura, A. (1982). Self-efficacy mechanism in human agency. *American psychologist*, 37(2), 122.

- Ceci, L. (2022). Mobile internet usage worldwide - statistics & facts. Retrieved from <https://www.statista.com/topics/779/mobile-internet/#dossierKeyfigures>
- Chatterjee, R., & Correia, A. P. (2020). Online students' attitudes toward collaborative learning and sense of community. *American Journal of Distance Education*, 34(1), 53-68.
- Chugh, R., & Ruhi, U. (2018). Social media in higher education: A literature review of Facebook. *Education and Information Technologies*, 23(2), 605-616. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-017-9621-2>
- Edgar, D. W. (2012). Learning theories and historical events affecting instructional design in education: Recitation literacy toward extraction literacy practices. *Sage Open*, 2(4), 2158244012462707.
- Herri, M., & Gunawan, S. (2020). The use of social media platform to promote authentic learning environment in higher education setting. *Science for Education Today*, 10(2), 105-123.
- International Telecommunication Union (ITU) (2020) ICT facts and figures 2020. Available at <https://www.itu.int/en/ITU-D/Statistics/Documents/facts/FactsFigures2020.pdf>.
- Jenaibi, B. A., & Mansoori, A. A. (2022). Use of social media in teaching high school students: A case of United Arab Emirates. *Contemporary Review of the Middle East*, 9(2), 158-183.
- Kazanidis, I., Pellas, N., Fotaris, P., & Tsinakos, A. (2018). Facebook and Moodle integration into instructional media design courses: A comparative analysis of students' learning experiences using the Community of Inquiry (CoI) model. *International Journal of Human-Computer Interaction*, 34(10), 932-942.
- Kuo, T. M., Tsai, C. C., & Wang, J. C. (2021). Linking web-based learning self-efficacy and learning engagement in MOOCs: The role of online academic hardiness. *The Internet and Higher Education*, 51, 100819.
- Lambton-Howard, D., Kiaer, J., & Kharrufa, A. (2021). 'Social media is their space': student and teacher use and perception of features of social media in language education. *Behaviour & Information Technology*, 40(16), 1700-1715.
- Manca, S. (2020). Snapping, pinning, liking or texting: Investigating social media in higher education beyond Facebook. *The Internet and Higher Education*, 44, 100707.
- Mohamed Farag Mohamed Aboudahr, S. (2020). The Effect of Using Youtube to Increase the Level of Listening Skills among Non-Native Students of Arabic Speakers in Malaysian Universities. *Education Quarterly Reviews*, 3(2). <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3612888>
- Pikhart, M. and Botezat, O. (2021). The impact of the use of social media on second language acquisition. *Procedia Computer Science*, 192, 1621-1628.
- Rieger, D. and Christoph, K. (2018). The daily dose of digital inspiration: a multi-method exploration of meaningful communication in social media. *New Media and Society*, 21(1), 97-118.
- Rozal, E., Ananda, R., Zb, A., Fauziddin, M., & Sulman, F. (2021). The Effect of Project-Based Learning through YouTube Presentations on English Learning Outcomes in Physics. *AL-Ishlah: Jurnal Pendidikan*, 13(3), 1924-1933.
- Scavarelli, A., Arya, A., & Teather, R. J. (2021). Virtual reality and augmented reality in social learning spaces: a literature review. *Virtual Reality*, 25(1), 257-277.
- Schunk, D. H., & Usher, E. L. (2011). Assessing self-efficacy for self-regulated learning. *Handbook of self-regulation of learning and performance*, 282-297.
- Sepulveda-Escobar, P., & Morrison, A. (2020). Online teaching placement during the COVID-19 pandemic in Chile: challenges and opportunities. *European Journal of Teacher Education*, 43(4), 587-607.
- Shodiyev, M. B. (2022). The usage of web technologies as social network (Facebook) in teaching a foreign language to adults. *Science and Education*, 3(2), 973-977.
- Simamora, R. M. (2020). The Challenges of online learning during the COVID-19 pandemic: An essay analysis of performing arts education students. *Studies in Learning and Teaching*, 1(2), 86-103.
- Yunus, M. M., Zakaria, S., & Suliman, A. (2019). The Potential Use of Social Media on Malaysian Primary Students to Improve Writing. *International Journal of Education and Practice*, 7(4), 450-458.